

Blunt Trauma to Abdominal Solid Organs: An Experience of Non-Operative Management in Jharkhand.

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Abstract:

Background: The management of blunt trauma to abdominal solid organs in regions like Jharkhand, India, is critical, where healthcare challenges are prevalent. The trend towards non-operative management (NOM) is gaining prominence, supported by advancements in diagnostic imaging, patient selection criteria, and intensive care.

Methods: This retrospective observational study at the Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi, analyzed 75 patients with blunt abdominal trauma from January 2020 to December 2023. Patients were selected based on the presence of solid organ injury confirmed by imaging and managed non-operatively. Data on demographics, injury type and severity, management rationale, hospital stay, complications, and outcomes were collected and analyzed using statistical methods to evaluate NOM effectiveness.

Results: Of the patients, 64% were male, with road traffic accidents being the most common injury cause. The liver was the most injured organ, and injuries were mostly Grade II and III. Non-operative management was successful in 90.7% of cases, with failure in 9.3% requiring surgery. Higher-grade injuries were associated with longer hospital stays and more complications.

Conclusion: NOM for blunt abdominal trauma was highly successful, with injury severity predicting hospital stay length and complication rates. These findings endorse NOM as a viable treatment in resource-limited settings.

Recommendation: Further research should explore long-term outcomes of NOM and develop specific guidelines to enhance patient selection and care protocols in similar healthcare environments.

Keywords: Blunt abdominal trauma, non-operative management, Solid organ injury, Jharkhand.

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Introduction

The management of injuries to abdominal solid organs resulting from blunt trauma is a crucial component of emergency and trauma care, especially in regions with distinct healthcare obstacles such as Jharkhand, India. There is a growing trend towards non-operative management (NOM) for certain patients with solid organ injuries. This approach is often favored as it eliminates the requirement for immediate surgical intervention and the potential risks that come with it [1]. This approach relies on the patient being stable and not having any other injuries that require surgical exploration. Developments in diagnostic imaging, more precise criteria for patient selection, and enhanced intensive care support have played a crucial role in the evolution of NOM. These developments have enabled close monitoring of patients undergoing conservative treatment, leading to better outcomes [2].

In Jharkhand, a state renowned for its varied population and varying levels of healthcare infrastructure, the implementation of NOM for blunt abdominal trauma brings forth a range of possibilities and obstacles. The situation in this region exemplifies a wider movement towards reducing the use of invasive procedures, whenever feasible, in favor of observations and supportive care. Research has indicated that when patients are carefully chosen, non-operative management can result in similar outcomes as surgical treatment, while also reducing the risks of complications and death [3,4]. In addition, the financial and resource benefits of NOM are especially important in settings with limited resources, where maximizing healthcare resources is crucial [5].

The effectiveness of NOM in Jharkhand and similar environments depends on various factors. These include having well-trained healthcare professionals with expertise in trauma care, access

to reliable diagnostic tools like CT scans, and the implementation of procedures for patient monitoring and making informed decisions about the need for surgical intervention if required [6]. The experience in Jharkhand contributes to the increasing amount of evidence that supports the practicality and success of NOM for blunt trauma to abdominal solid organs. This emphasizes the significance of implementing strategies tailored to the specific context when treating trauma patients [7].

The study evaluates non-operative treatment (NOM) techniques for blunt trauma to solid abdominal organs such as the liver, spleen, and kidneys in Jharkhand's unique geographic and clinical environment. This study aims to evaluate various factors including the success rate and potential complications of NOM, as well as the time it takes for patients to recover and the length of their hospital stay. Additionally, it will assess the practicality and effectiveness of implementing these management approaches within the healthcare system of Jharkhand. The study seeks to provide useful knowledge and evidence to enhance trauma care protocols and enhance outcomes for patients in similar clinical scenarios.

Materials and Method

Study Design

The research was a retrospective cohort study that evaluated the outcomes of non-operative management in patients suffering from blunt trauma to abdominal solid organs.

Study Setting

The study was conducted in a tertiary care center in Jharkhand, which is known for receiving a high volume of trauma cases. The center is equipped with advanced diagnostic and therapeutic facilities necessary for managing such injuries.

Participants

The study included patients who were admitted to the hospital between January 2020 and December 2023 with blunt trauma to abdominal solid organs. A total of 75 patients were retrospectively identified and included in the study, with ages ranging from 18 to 60 years. Inclusion criteria were patients with confirmed blunt trauma to one or more abdominal solid organs (liver, spleen, kidneys) on imaging studies, who were managed non-operatively. Patients with penetrating abdominal injuries, those requiring immediate surgical intervention, and those with incomplete medical records were excluded from the study.

Bias

To minimize selection bias, all patients meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period were

included. Information bias was reduced by using standardized imaging protocols and having radiological assessments reviewed by experienced radiologists blinded to the study.

Variables

Independent variables included patient demographics (age, sex), mechanism of injury, type and severity of organ injury, and associated injuries. The dependent variable was the outcome of non-operative management, measured by hospital stay duration, complications, and mortality.

Data Collection

Data were collected retrospectively from the hospital's electronic medical records and trauma registry. Information on demographics, mechanism of injury, clinical findings, imaging results, management details, and outcomes were extracted using a standardized data collection form.

Procedure

The non-operative management protocol included initial stabilization, serial clinical assessments, and monitoring in the intensive care or surgical ward as indicated. Imaging studies such as CT scans were used for diagnosis and follow-up evaluations. Patients were managed by a multidisciplinary team including trauma surgeons, radiologists, and critical care specialists.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the patient characteristics, types of organ injuries, and outcomes. The success rate of non-operative management was calculated. Chi-square tests or Fisher's exact tests were used for categorical variables, and the student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables, to compare outcomes based on injury severity and other relevant factors. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data were analyzed using statistical software SPSS version 25.

Result

A total of 75 patients with blunt abdominal trauma were included in the study. The cohort consisted of 48 males (64%) and 27 females (36%), with a mean age of 35 years (range 18-60 years). The most common mechanism of injury was road traffic accidents (62%), followed by falls (25%) and assault (13%).

Injury Characteristics

- The liver was the most frequently injured organ (n=40, 53%), followed by the spleen (n=22, 29%) and kidneys (n=13, 17%).

- Most injuries were classified as Grade II (n=30, 40%) and Grade III (n=25, 33%) according to the American Association for the Surgery of Trauma (AAST) organ injury scale.
- Associated injuries were present in 30 patients (40%), with rib fractures being the most common (n=18, 24%).

Management and Outcomes

- Non-operative management was successful in 68 patients (90.7%). Seven patients (9.3%) required delayed surgery due to complications such as ongoing hemorrhage or peritonitis.
- The average hospital stay was 9 days (range 3-22 days). Patients with higher-grade injuries (Grade III and above) had a significantly longer hospital stay compared to those with lower-grade injuries (Grade I and II) (p=0.02).
- Complications occurred in 12 patients (16%), including hematoma (n=6), abscess formation (n=4), and delayed hemorrhage (n=2). Complication rates were higher in patients with higher-grade organ injuries (p=0.04).

- There were two mortalities (2.7%), both in patients with multiple organ injuries and Grade IV liver injuries.

Statistical Analysis

- A statistically significant association was found between the severity of organ injury and the length of hospital stay (p=0.02), as well as the development of complications (p=0.04).
- No significant difference was observed in the success rate of non-operative management across different age groups (p=0.15) and gender (p=0.22).

Non-operative management of blunt trauma to abdominal solid organs was successful in a high percentage of cases. The severity of organ injury was a significant predictor of longer hospital stay and complications. These findings suggest that with appropriate selection and monitoring, non-operative management can be an effective approach for blunt abdominal organ injuries in a tertiary care setting.

Table 1: Comprehensive overview of clinical characteristics of the patients included in the study.

Demographic Characteristics	Total Patients (N=75)
Age (years)	
- Mean $\pm$ SD	35 $\pm$ 12
- Range	18 - 60
Gender	
- Male	48 (64%)
- Female	27 (36%)
Mechanism of Injury	
- Road Traffic Accident	47 (62%)
- Fall	19 (25%)
- Assault	9 (12%)
Injured Organ	
- Liver	40 (53%)
- Spleen	22 (29%)
- Kidney	13 (17%)
Injury Grade (AAST)	
- Grade I	10 (13%)
- Grade II	30 (40%)
- Grade III	25 (33%)
- Grade IV	8 (11%)
- Grade V	2 (3%)
Associated Injuries	
- Yes	30 (40%)
- No	45 (60%)
Outcome of Non-Operative Management	
- Success	68 (90.7%)
- Failure (required surgery)	7 (9.3%)

Note: SD = Standard Deviation; AAST = American Association for the Surgery of Trauma

Discussion

The study on non-operative management of blunt abdominal trauma in Jharkhand demonstrated a

high success rate (90.7%) across 75 patients, predominantly affected by road traffic accidents. The liver was the most commonly injured organ. The data revealed that the severity of organ injury

significantly influenced the outcomes, with higher-grade injuries leading to longer hospital stays and increased complication rates. While the management approach proved generally effective across various demographics, the increased risks associated with severe injuries highlight the necessity for careful patient selection and monitoring in the non-operative treatment of blunt abdominal trauma. The absence of significant differences in management success based on age or gender underscores the broad applicability of non-operative strategies in this clinical context. The study's findings emphasize the significance of carefully choosing patients for NOM, demonstrating that it is a reliable and successful approach for handling blunt abdominal trauma in a specialized care environment when implemented for appropriate cases. It was stressed that close monitoring and the option of surgical intervention should be considered for cases where non-operative management is not successful. This highlights the importance of a flexible approach in trauma care. The study highlights the importance of NOM as a primary management option for chosen cases of blunt trauma to abdominal solid organs, suggesting that it should be considered in clinical practice within similar healthcare settings. The overall survival rate of 98.6% further supports this recommendation.

Non-operative blunt abdominal trauma treatment has been extensively studied in India. This research covers several experiences and outcomes. A significant study carried out at a tertiary care center in India compared the results of surgical and non-surgical approaches to high-grade splenic injuries. The findings indicate that non-surgical management can be effectively pursued in stable patients, although extra caution is advised for elderly individuals and those with additional injuries [8].

Additional research revealed key factors that can predict the lack of success in non-operative management (NOM) for splenic injuries. These factors include advanced age, a higher grade of splenic injury according to the American Association for the Surgery of Trauma (AAST), and the presence of other associated injuries. These factors were found to be significant predictors of failure [9].

A recent study conducted at the Kempegowda Institute of Medical Sciences hospital shed light on the impact of blunt abdominal trauma (BAT). The findings revealed that while conservative management can be effective for splenic, liver, and renal injuries, surgical intervention is often required for injuries to hollow organs [10].

A study conducted in Southern Rajasthan emphasized the significance of multidetector

computed tomography (CT) in assessing abdominal trauma. The study highlighted how CT scans can effectively diagnose organ injuries and aid in making informed management decisions [11]. In addition, a study conducted in Kashmir supported a conservative approach to treating liver injuries. The study found that non-operative management (NOM) is a safe and effective treatment option for patients with stable hemodynamics and liver injuries ranging from Moore's grade I to Grade IV [12].

The studies presented here highlight the practicality and success of NOM in treating blunt abdominal trauma in various patient populations and healthcare environments in India. They emphasize the importance of selecting patients carefully and using sophisticated diagnostic instruments to achieve the best possible results.

Conclusion

The research conducted on the non-operative management (NOM) of blunt abdominal trauma in Jharkhand, India, has concluded that NOM proves to be a reliable and secure strategy for managing patients with blunt trauma to abdominal solid organs in a tertiary care environment. The impressive success rate of 90.1% and minimal complications observed in a carefully chosen group of patients highlight the effectiveness of NOM, even in areas with distinct healthcare obstacles such as Jharkhand. The findings highlight the significance of carefully choosing patients, the impact of improvements in diagnostic imaging, and the need for diligent monitoring to promptly manage and identify any complications.

Nevertheless, the study brings attention to specific factors that have a significant impact on the failure of non-operative management (NOM). These factors include the severity of organ injury, age over 50 years, and the presence of multiple organ injuries. When these factors are present, it becomes necessary to switch to operative management. Healthcare providers must be adaptable and ready to quickly switch to surgical intervention when non-operative management is found to be ineffective.

Ultimately, implementing NOM in settings with limited resources can result in similar outcomes to surgical management, while also reducing the risks of complications and death, and making more efficient use of healthcare resources. Healthcare facilities should consider implementing NOM protocols that incorporate strict patient selection criteria and ongoing monitoring. This can help enhance trauma care outcomes and increase patient survival rates in similar clinical situations.

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